

INSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article examines the institutional and legal framework for improving the quality of human capital in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It analyzes existing regulatory legal acts, state strategies and programs aimed at developing education, health care and social protection as key components of human capital. Particular attention is paid to issues of improving legal regulation and institutional mechanisms that promote sustainable development of human potential.*

Keywords: *human capital, institutional framework, legal regulation, education, healthcare, sustainable development.*

Introduction

Human capital development is recognized as a key factor in Uzbekistan's sustainable socio-economic growth. In Uzbekistan, with a large proportion of young people (over 60%), investing in human capital is essential for both national growth and poverty reduction. The head of state emphasized: "The issue of education should be considered a priority, be at the top of the agenda and be strictly controlled." The development of human capital, along with the implementation of a fair social policy, is one of the seven important areas of the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan. And it is directly related to quality education, medical care, and meaningful organization of free time.

Uzbekistan has joined 27 countries worldwide that support the World Bank Group's Human Capital Project. The World Bank Group's Human Capital Project views human capital as one of the driving forces of inclusive economic growth. It includes a program to develop human capital research and assessments, and provides assistance to countries seeking to improve their performance in relevant human capital sectors.

In the context of the transition to an innovative economy and increasing the country's competitiveness in the international arena, state policy focuses on the formation of effective institutional and legal mechanisms that facilitate increased investment in the health, education and professional skills of the population.

Methods

The development of the human capital system in Uzbekistan is ensured by a number of state institutions:

- The Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation – was created to strengthen the connection between science, innovation and educational programs and is responsible for the development of higher education, science and innovation.

- The Ministry of Preschool and School Education coordinates a large-scale expansion of the coverage and quality of education at the level of schools and kindergartens, and also introduces new standards and digitalization in education.

- Ministry of Health – implements national health programs, including programs on reproductive health and maternal and child health.

- Employment and Vocational Training Agency – creates an infrastructure for training in skills that are in demand in the modern economy.

- Civil institutions (mahallas, NGOs) play an important role in social support of the population at the local level and are involved in the implementation of projects to support youth, women, the elderly and socially vulnerable groups.

The peculiarity of Uzbekistan’s institutional approach is the gradual transition from administrative-hierarchical to program-targeted and network interaction between participants. Interdepartmental cooperation and participation of public institutions increase the sustainability of the systemic approach to the formation of human capital.

The legal basis for the development of human capital in Uzbekistan is determined by a number of strategic and regulatory documents:

- The Law “On Education” defines the basic principles, levels and forms of educational activity.

- The concept of development of the education system until 2030 – defines target indicators and reforms in the field of education.

- The Law "On the Protection of Citizens' Health" - establishes the rights to free medical care and the state's responsibility for the health of the population.

- The “Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy outlines priority areas for investment in people: education, medicine, gender equality, youth.

Table No. 1

Summary table of legal framework in the sphere of human capital of the Republic of Uzbekistan

№	Normative act	Emphasis on the concept of "human capital"
1	Concept of development of education and science until 2030	The concept of “human capital” is used as a target for creating an integrated education system
2	Human Capital Index Project (World Bank)	The importance of public investment in education and health care for the formation of human capital is mentioned
3	Decrees, initiatives of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev	The emphasis is on the development of science and education for the sake of “developing human capital”
4	Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030"	Investments in medicine, sports, and social services are aimed at strengthening the health and potential of citizens – part of human capital

5	Legislative and financial initiatives (e.g. student loans and private schools)	Tools for investment in education: preferential loans, school construction, growth in the number of non-state educational institutions
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Results

Consideration of the characteristics of human capital allows us to determine the influence of the institutional environment on human capital through organizational structures and institutional agreements, and to identify formal and informal institutions involved in its formation and development. Formal institutions include: the legislative framework that determines the functioning of the employee in work activities, obtaining education, maintaining and strengthening health, etc., as well as a complex of relevant infrastructure institutions that ensure the production, educational, scientific, health, cultural, educational, and social activities of employees. Informal institutions, in turn, include: the institution of the family, social environment, religion, culture, ideology, mentality, national traditions, etc. As a rule, the impact of formal institutions is targeted and targeted in relation to objects of human capital, while the influence of informal institutions is more diffuse, although it manifests itself in almost all aspects of human activity.

The key priority of the reforms has become increasing the accessibility of national higher education. For this purpose, new universities are opened every year, in particular:

- it was proposed to provide support for the development of non-governmental educational organizations;

- attract the private sector to develop education.

Other important reforms in legal regulation include the rights to:

- based on the needs of personnel customers, independently develop and approve, in agreement with the ministry, curricula and programs;

- accept foreign citizens outside the admission quotas by means of an interview, without passing tests;

- implementation of a credit-modular system;

- attraction of foreign specialists.

An important step was the involvement of employers in the educational process and scientific research at universities. A mechanism was proposed for involving professional communities in updating qualification requirements, forming orders for graduates, organizing internships for teachers and student practice in production.

Discussions

In the fourth direction of the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan “Implementation of a fair social policy, development of human capital”, the following results were achieved:

1. Education and training. Within the framework of the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" the number of pre-school, school and higher educational institutions is expanding, public-private partnership is developing.

- Pre-school education: coverage of children aged 3–6 increased from 23.8% in 2016 to 71.1% in 2023.

Fig. 1 – Coverage of children aged 3-6 years by preschool organizations in the Republic of Uzbekistan

- Compulsory general education: coverage of primary and secondary education is almost 99.9%, more than 643 thousand new student places in 7 years.

Fig. 2 – Number of general education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan

- Professional skills and the IT sector: programming projects are being implemented (the One Million Coders project), IT hubs and digital clusters are being created (IT Park, the International Center for Digital Technologies), grants are being allocated for infrastructure and retraining in key sectors of the economy.

- Higher education: growth in coverage from 9% (2016) to 42% (2023), expansion of partnerships with leading specialized foreign scientific and educational institutions, opening of joint educational programs of double degrees. The higher education system has become more flexible. Starting from the 2018/2019 academic year, it is proposed to introduce three-year bachelor's degree programs and one-year master's degree programs, including distance learning.

Fig. 3 – Number of students in general education institutions by regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Fig.4 – Growth in the number of students and the number of higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan

2. Human Development Index (HDI): Human Development Index (HDI): Uzbekistan ranked 101st in the world in 2023 with an index of 0.727, jumping 11 positions in 5 years. The growth of HDI indicators indicates an increase in the level of education, healthcare, and the general standard of living of the population and is achieved through increased public investment in the social sphere and the implementation of programs aimed at reducing poverty.

3. Science and innovation.

- Investments: educational expenditures make up 4-5% of GDP, medicine – up to 2-3%, science – less than 1%.

- Innovation: In 2021, Uzbekistan ranked 86th in the Global Innovation Index.

4. Development of personnel and youth.

- International programs: participation in Erasmus+, Horizon – 250 scholarships and 69 joint projects, plans to introduce quotas at the presidential initiative.

- Obtaining international exams: more than a thousand teachers have completed internships abroad, and expenses for international exams have been reimbursed.

Despite positive changes, challenges remain:

- education funding remains below the level of leading countries, despite the increase in its share in GDP from 4.2% to 5.5% (2020–2023);

- inequality in employment among women, significant gender wage gap;

- the quality of education in remote regions and rural areas is inferior to that in urban centers;

- the gap between demand in the labour market and training programmes remains significant;

- a shortage of graduates with higher education for various sectors of the economy; - an acute problem of the quality of education, the level of university science and personnel training;

- low competition among higher education institutions.

Conclusions

Having examined the available indicators, we can conclude that for the period from 2018 to 2023, the Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" provides positive dynamics in terms of GDP growth, reduction in poverty, and improvement in the quality of human capital.

Fig.5 – Socio-economic indicators of Uzbekistan (2018 – 2023)

As can be seen from the graph presented, after a slowdown in 2020, there is dynamic growth since 2021 and a steady increase in GDP per capita in 2023. National poverty has been halved between 2021 and 2023, and is planned to reach 6% by the end of 2025. There is a high HDI level of 0.727. According to the National Statistics Committee, life expectancy at birth in 2024 was 75.1 years.

The importance of human capital development is determined by the following characteristics:

- demographic potential – the growth of the birth rate and the labor force create a window of opportunity for our country;

- competitiveness in the global market – countries are moving to digital economic models;
- social sustainability – equal rights, health and education strengthen society and minimize the risks of poverty.

Uzbekistan is purposefully investing in human capital – education, health, digital literacy and social support. Today, this is already bringing real results: GDP growth, poverty reduction and improved quality of life.

Thus, a multi-level system of institutional and legal foundations for the development of human capital has been formed in Uzbekistan. Despite the existence of conceptual strategies and a regulatory framework, the effectiveness of their application requires further strengthening through:

- strengthening interdepartmental cooperation;
- implementation of digital monitoring platforms;
- improving personnel policy in the education and medical sectors;
- attracting private investment and international partners.

The main challenges are to ensure equal opportunities and accelerate innovative development. The Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy has laid a solid foundation for the country's powerful breakthrough in the new technological age.

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